

CREDIBLE
EU carbon farming

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Second report on the activities of the Focus Group on “An effective policy mix for scaling up carbon farming”

Project CREDIBLE: “Building momentum and trust to achieve credible soil carbon farming in the EU”.

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Executive summary

This document is part of the EU-funded project CREDIBLE, Grant Agreement 101112951, and it captures the main outputs of the second round of conversations had within the Focus Group on “An effective policy mix for scaling up carbon farming”.

The main goal of this Focus Group is to generate recommendations/opinions that could be used in the development/deployment of relevant policies around carbon farming, and particularly in the definition of the Carbon Removal Certification Framework. These informed opinions have emerged through the active participation of experts (details provided in Tables 1 and 2) in a number of activities (listed in Table 3).

In order to convey the recommendations to the broader possible audience, the following sections have been included in the document: i) an introduction, which helps clarifying the problem and why addressing this topic was considered important by the CREDIBLE consortium; ii) a process report, which summarises the conversations held by the Focus Group, highlighting the key points and tensions that emerged and; iii) a summary of recommendations, listing in a concise way the opinion of the Focus Group on how to best solve some of these tensions.

1. Focus Group participation and activities

Table 1 - Partners of CREDIBLE who participated in the Focus Group.

Name of the expert	Affiliation	Role*	Country
Mathieu Mal	EEB European Environmental Bureau	Lead	Belgium
Hugh McDonald	Ecologic Institute	Member	Germany
Julia Pazmino Murillo	Ecologic Institute	Member	Germany
Julia Grimault	I4CE Institute for Climate Economics	Member	France

* Lead (of the Focus Group); Member; Rapporteur; Observer...

Table 2 - Members of the Focus Group external to CREDIBLE.

Name of the expert	Affiliation	Role*	Country
Lisa Wiatschka	Bax & Company	Member	Spain
Hinse Boonstra	Bayer Crop Science	Member	Netherlands
Riccardo Gambini	BirdLife	Member	Belgium
Wijnand Stoefs	Carbon Market Watch	Member	Belgium
Marlène Ramón Hernández	Carbon Market Watch	Member	Belgium
Aalt van Middendorp	CEJA	Member	Belgium
Tsjerk Terpstra	DG AGRI	Member	Belgium
Emmanuel Petel	DG AGRI	Member	Belgium
Chiara Micelli	DG CLIMA	Member	Belgium
Hendrik Goris	DG CLIMA	Member	Belgium
Ania Foszczynski	DG COMP	Member	Belgium
Lucie Veteau	DG COMP	Member	Belgium
Marc Rosiers	ELO European Landowners' Organization	Member	Belgium
Ana Rocha	ELO European Landowners' Organization	Member	Belgium
Julia Bognar	IEEP Institute for European Environmental Policy	Member	Belgium

Hanna Winkler	IFOAM Organics Europe	Member	Belgium
Casper Zulim de Swarte	OP2B One Planet Business for Biodiversity	Member	Netherlands
Emmanuel de Laroche	The Shifters	Member	France
Alan Matthews	Trinity College Dublin	Member	Ireland
Matilde Fachini	Wetlands International	Member	Belgium

* Lead (of the Focus Group); Member; Rapporteur; Observer...

Table 3 - List of main activities carried out to steer the conversations.

General description of the activity	Date of execution
Online workshop: CAP and CRCF	17/01/25
Online workshop: NRL, SML, and CRCF	23/01/25
Online workshop: CRCF business case	31/01/25

2. Introduction

Policy environments are complex, and with the Carbon Removals and Carbon Farming Regulation (CRCF), a new and different type of policy is added into the mix of policies that can influence agricultural land management. If the policy mix is to be conducive to the enhanced uptake of “carbon farming” practices that enhance carbon sequestration in biogenic carbon pools, special attention needs to be paid to the possible interactions, synergies, and tensions between the different policies and frameworks.

CRCF certification methodologies, including the one for agriculture on mineral soils, are currently at draft stage. A central aspect of developing the methodology is the question of suitable indicators, for Soil Organic Carbon (SOC) quantification, and sustainability. In the quantification section, the draft agriculture methodology made available in October 2024 uses SOC stock and Soil Bulk Density as indicators. In the sustainability section, the minimum sustainability criteria build on the EU Taxonomy’s technical screening criteria established to implement the Do No Significant Harm (DNSH) principle, where these are available. For the mandatory biodiversity co-benefits, the draft methodology refers to two of the indicators described in the Article 11 of the Nature Restoration Law, namely SOC and high diversity landscape features. The current draft methodology’s mandatory co-benefit requirement would be met if a carbon farming project increased soil organic carbon. Alternatively, it proposes to make use of the positive list of practices under Annex VII of the NRL. Selecting the appropriate indicators is not only a matter of internal relevance for the new policy, but also ensuring external coherence by taking into account the existing and developing policy mix.

This document reflects the presentations and discussions held on three separate occasions in January 2025 in the context of Focus Group 2.3 under the CREDIBLE project. The areas of focus during these sessions have been the Common Agricultural Policy, the Soil Monitoring Law, the Nature Restoration Law, and the “CRCF business case” which considers elements from voluntary corporate action and the ongoing discussions around compliance instruments for climate change mitigation action in the agri-food value chain. The overarching question when discussing these policy areas was: what can the CRCF and these other policy elements learn from each other and how can they, maximising synergies, lead to a conducive policy environment for robust carbon farming at scale?

3. Process report

Common Agricultural Policy

The Common Agricultural Policy (CAP) sets a number of specific objectives that directly relate to climate change and environmental protection, and therefore enable the CAP to connect with, and contribute to carbon farming. Mandatory conditionality, which includes management practices with environmental benefits, applies to all area- and animal-based support. On top of that, Member States (MS) are required to design relevant interventions through Eco-schemes and Agro-Environmental Commitments, to which they allocate dedicated funding. The implementation of these measures and their outcomes is subject to evaluation through the Performance Monitoring and Evaluation Framework (PMEF). This Framework uses a set of indicators to track MS spending, progress towards targets, and impacts on a series of variables.

Whereas many of the CAP indicators (interestingly, also those called “result indicators”) are in fact practice- or activity-based at macro level (MS or EU level), the CRCF is explicitly results- or outcome-based at farm level. Therefore, the share of land under commitments, such as collected under the CAP result indicators does not help with CRCF quantification. The CRCF requires the change in carbon stocks or emissions to be quantified. Quantification would be based on a measure-remeasure soil sample approach or a model-based approach. The use of remote sensing technologies, which are still under development and are at this stage not fully able to provide all needed information, is also under consideration to support the quantification.

Box 1: Indicator framework under the CAP

Output indicators monitor the payments units under certain schemes (number of farmers, projects, hectares, animals, etc.).

Result indicators link all interventions in the CAP to their desired result (share of Utilised Agricultural Area (UAA) or Livestock Units (LSU) under certain commitments to reach a specific objective). For example, 2.5% of LSU is covered by commitments to reduce emissions (including manure management), 35% of UAA to reduce emissions or maintain or enhance carbon storage (in grassland, permanent crops, and cultivated wet- and peatland), and 47.5% of UAA to improve soil quality and biota (reduced tillage, cover crops, leguminous crops in the rotation). Since eligible interventions are designed at MS level, uptake of practices and contribution to specific objectives varies widely across the EU as illustrated by the graph below. In the future, there could be a political discussion on whether more specific relevant interventions will be imposed on MS for inclusion in their CAP Strategic Plan (CSP).

Figure 1: Result indicator Carbon storage in soils and biomass (%UAA) across EU MS (DG AGRI [Agri-food Data Portal](#))

Context and impact indicators are based on data and statistics that are collected, for example through LUCAS or LULUCF data from the national inventories, including some indicators on soil carbon and greenhouse gasses, but also indicators on water use and quality from Eurostat.

Under an evaluation exercise the Commission goes a step further beyond the aggregated data of intervention result indicators at MS or EU level, for example “Carbon storage in soils and biomass as share of UAA” or “Share of utilised agricultural area (UAA) under supported commitments beneficial for soil management to improve soil quality and biota”, by labelling specific practices (fallow land, intercropping, cover crops, etc.), which are set up under interventions. Then, for each practice, the estimated area on which the practice is applied is multiplied with a coefficient, to estimate roughly the GHG emission reduction or carbon sequestration potential of the interventions under the CAP Strategic Plans.

From 2025, Member States have to report on output and result indicators on a yearly basis, in their Annual Performance Report, to demonstrate how their spending has progressed on the way to achieving the targets set in their CAP Strategic Plans. To allow for better analysis on the implementation of the CAP’s green architecture, MS will be required to also provide disaggregated data on their interventions. The EU Commission in turn has the responsibility for reporting on CAP budget effectiveness, efficiency, relevance, and coherence to the EU Parliament and Council.

The CAP's soil organic carbon context indicator looks at soil organic carbon in arable land and is based on the JRC's LUCAS data. In principle, LUCAS surveys are carried out every three years, but this soil module, perhaps only every six to nine years. In fact, at this moment, there are only two data points, 2009 and 2018. These are of course national or regional level indicators, not farm level indicators. They can be useful to monitor impact of interventions over time, but not in terms of quantifying changes that individual farmers might make on their farms. The Integrated Administration and Control System (IACS) under CAP consisting of a combination of Land Parcel Identification System (LPIS) which provides high-level land cover information and Geospatial Aid Applications (GSA) used by farmers, will allow even more granular monitoring of practice implementation. The LPIS is mainly used to verify the eligibility of land areas for area-based direct payments with very detailed parcel-based information. The tool could be extended to collect technical data regarding land use, such as the use of cover crops at farm level. This data can be relevant to follow the farming activity in relation with carbon farming. Places where this information could come into carbon farming schemes are as data partially underpinning the CRCF standardised baseline, or feeding into the model-based certification approach which could include data from the LPIS as well as more environmental context and impact indicators. Combining all this information in the model may allow for more robust predictions of what the outcomes can be. When it comes to the CRCF sustainability requirements, it is unclear how much information the CAP declarations capture on this.

Through their farm management plans, farmers are providing a significant amount of farm-level activity data to CAP managing authorities for payment purposes, although this information is not necessarily public or harmonised across the EU. They also provide a range of data to comply with other regulations, such as the Nitrates Directive for which they already need to have some kind of bookkeeping to prove compliance, and schemes or certifications such as organic agriculture labels, depending on the MS and their value chains. Decision support apps (including carbon footprint calculators), which many farmers are already using to monitor emissions among other things, and based on which some develop climate mitigation and adaptation plans are also rich sources of data that have not been considered as part of the CRCF certification methodology. Companies are already working with farmers based on all this data, but it is a challenging task, given the lack of interoperability between the different sources. Harmonising indicators and requirements could reduce the complexity and alleviate the burden of having to monitor

similar things in different ways and feeding them into different formats and systems. There should be special attention to making use of existing information, as information requirements may deter farmers from engaging in new schemes.

Box 2: Data gathered by farmers

- Crop and Land Use Data: Information on the types of crops grown, crop rotation practices, and land use changes.
- Nutrient Management: Data on the use of fertilisers and manure, including quantities and application methods.
- Pesticide Use: Information on the types and amounts of pesticides used, as well as integrated pest management practices.
- Soil Management Practices: Details on soil conservation measures, such as cover cropping, reduced tillage, liming, and organic matter management.
- Water Management: Reporting on irrigation practices, water usage, and measures to protect water quality.
- Biodiversity Measures: Data on actions taken to preserve and enhance biodiversity, such as maintaining hedgerows, buffer strips, and habitats for wildlife.
- Greenhouse Gas Emissions: Information on practices aimed at reducing greenhouse gas emissions, such as methane reduction strategies in livestock farming.
- Yield.
- Soil health: Nutrients, Ph, texture, SOC.

As shown, the CAP covers and funds a lot of activities that fall under carbon farming and should continue to do so. Many MS also implement relevant measures in their CSP, but research shows that despite a significant share of land being under voluntary actions for both carbon sequestration and nitrous oxide emissions reduction, historically, CAP support has not had a positive effect on [carbon stocks](#). This can mean that at the same time, the policy drives practices that have [adverse effects](#), or that the system of [Eco-schemes](#) (which are predominantly used on an annual basis) is not sufficient to ensure continued practices and results. While the current CAP is [greener](#) than its predecessors, and has [some potential](#) to enhance carbon sequestration, it is still considered to [fall short of turning around](#) the emissions and sequestration profile of the sector, and [meeting the EU's climate and environment](#) objectives. This track record has led to criticism of the activity-based approach, and is sometimes used to make the case for investing in a result-based system. Result-based schemes, however, are not without challenges. Striking the balance between a robust and practical MRV system remains one of the stumbling blocks in the CRCF design. Result-based schemes can turn out to be quite expensive and their MRV and certification process can make up a significant share of their cost, requiring a high carbon price to make the effort worthwhile. The current CAP offers considerable flexibility to MS to design policy that suits the national context. However, this means that the interventions and the practices it facilitates differ from

country to country. The CRCF, on the other hand, is an EU-wide regulation which does not depend on MS action, and could therefore provide equal incentives across the EU, be it for now on a voluntary basis.

Although the information gathered under the CAP evolves to become more granular on the type of interventions and practices at farm level, coming closer to what is needed in a result-based carbon farming scheme, it may still not match the level of detail and scrutiny required under the CRCF. Transforming the CAP as a whole to result-based incentives and using its funds to monitor SOC at parcel level will be challenging, may not be cost-effective, might unnecessarily divert public funds from more suitable destinations such as the actual implementation of the interventions, may not benefit smaller farms, and risks meeting regulatory limitations under competition law (see section on public-private funding).

Soil Monitoring Law

The Soil Monitoring Law (SML) was proposed by the Commission in 2023 as part of the Soil Strategy that was adopted in 2021. It is a proposal for a Directive that aims to fill a legal gap that was existing because there was no EU law on soils yet. The law has a non-binding objective for achieving healthy soils by 2050, a set of definitions, sets out common rules for a soil health monitoring and assessment framework and includes some requirements for a more sustainable management of EU soils. It is currently at the political trilogue stage, and therefore not yet final. With the expected adoption of the final law in 2025, MS have until 2027 to transpose the Directive into national law, and the first monitoring and assessment cycle would be around 2030, repeating four more times by 2050.

The SML text mentions the CRCF, and from the beginning there has been a clear desire from policy makers to create synergies between the files, but given the different timelines and scales, the details on how exactly this would work, remain unclear. During the current SML negotiations, interactions or tensions with the CRCF do not seem to be a major point of attention either. The Commission proposal includes an Article on Sustainable Soil Management that requires Member States to define and gradually implement a set of sustainable soil management practices, on the basis of an Annex with broad sustainable soil management principles. However, the EU Parliament position significantly reduced this article, deleting most of its core obligations and maintaining only some elements relating to advice and capacity building towards farmers. Ongoing negotiations on the law will decide on the final wording of this article.

The SML uses the term descriptors rather than indicators, and as the law is still under negotiation, different options are being considered. To monitor the change in SOC, the institutions propose the Soil Organic Carbon Concentration (gC per kg) rather than the Soil Organic Carbon Stock proposed under the CRCF. The Council position currently adds Soil Organic Carbon Stocks (tC per ha) as an additional metric. All institutions propose the monitoring of bulk density in top- and subsoil. The CRCF draft methodology and the SML proposal refer to the same standards for quantifying SOC (ISO 10694) and bulk density in top- and subsoil (ISO 11272). However, whereas the CRCF sets a soil sampling depth of at least 30 cm, this was not part of the Commission's SML proposal, but brought to the negotiation table by the Parliament, and is still under negotiation. The sampling efforts under the SML would result in about 200,000 sampling points across

the EU, organised at soil district/unit level (sizes can differ per MS and are subject to political decision) across the EU, and across land uses, which is of limited significance to individual CRCF projects, considering the plot-level scale of sampling required there. However, this data could be relevant for the establishment of the standardised baselines which are likely to be implemented in the CRCF.

The SML also aims to include a descriptor for soil biodiversity. While SOC might be seen by some as a proxy for biodiversity, and that it is proposed as a biodiversity indicator under the CRCF, in line with Article 11 of the Nature Restoration Law, in the SML discussions, it was clear from the start that the loss of soil biodiversity should be measured by a tailored descriptor. Soil biodiversity is extremely complex, and the science around it is still under development. To measure it, many scientists use a combination of different descriptors. In the SML, the Commission has proposed to use Soil Basal Respiration as the main descriptor, with other descriptors being optional, but also this has been criticised by the scientific community for not being sufficiently robust. To monitor and assess soil biodiversity, scientists state that it is important to look at both the taxonomic diversity (which species are there) and functional biodiversity (what role do they play). Hence a combination of indicators is required. The Parliament position on the SML moves in this direction by proposing, among other descriptors, taxonomic diversity based on metabarcoding, and population abundance of bacteria, archaea, fungi, nematodes, and pathogenic fungi. The Council lists a number of descriptors, including some of those proposed by the Parliament, and suggests that at least one of those should be selected for monitoring.

The biodiversity indicators that are on the SML negotiation table may not be suitable for direct implementation in farm-level monitoring for the CRCF. Indicators for a limited frequency scientific monitoring exercise at regional level, may not be fit for purpose for plot-level credit certification where the feasibility and cost of MRV need to be taken into account. There is a fair balance to be struck between the robustness of the results and the practical accessibility of a scheme to be adopted by individual farmers.

The SML considers only below ground biodiversity, while in the CRCF this is not specified. The CRCF mentions “biodiversity, including soil health, and the avoidance of land degradation”, leaving open the option to consider above or below ground biodiversity, or both. From an integrity and robustness angle, there is a strong case for evaluating both in the CRCF, but given the current cost and knowledge challenges with soil biodiversity, the CRCF may have to start with an above ground biodiversity indicator.

Even for above ground biodiversity, the same challenge is present to some degree. The Commission is looking to provide tools that deliver sustainability that are fit for purpose, that enable action as fast as possible and cost effectively and that can be used in every Member State regardless of the starting point of the local context. As a result, the Commission is currently considering whether, contrary to the quantification of carbon, biodiversity should, in a first phase, be activity-based, for example by considering activities listed under Annex VII of the NRL. This option, however, is seen by some as insufficient to guarantee the safeguarding of biodiversity as intended, since it would come down to how restrictive the list of allowed practices would be and how clearly they would be defined, and it would not take into account varying local effects as a single action can yield significantly different results depending on where it is implemented. Inspiration can also be drawn from existing sustainable agriculture schemes. The CREDIBLE stakeholder focus group exploring the operationalisation of sustainability in the CRCF carbon farming in agriculture methodology [proposes](#) a mandatory activity-based approach to demonstrate compliance with the sustainability criteria, and a voluntary additional result-based certification of biodiversity assuming this would generate a price premium that would incentivise additional efforts. The [Regen10 framework](#), for example, suggests metrics such as number of wild species on the farm, number of crop species, indicator species for habitat quality, alongside other indicators, also for wider sustainability objectives.

Monitoring a set of indicators and gathering data is only the beginning. The data also needs to be interpreted and evaluated, which currently still proves challenging due to a lack in depth of understanding of our soils and the lack of comprehensive databases. Soil biodiversity is a rapidly evolving field of research, and the monitoring as well as the evaluation methods will keep developing together with the scientific understanding of soil species and their interactions. To assess soil health under the SML, the Commission proposes to apply EU-wide thresholds for some of the indicators, MS-set thresholds for other indicators, and also a category of indicators which will have to be monitored, but not assessed against any threshold.

Finally, there is the question of the availability and accessibility of the data that is collected under the SML. Whereas the CRCF requires GNSS coordinates for the soil samples, and the information will be made available in a centralised public registry, there are still a lot of questions around the format and level of detail in which SML data will be made available.

The European Parliament and Council have proposed changes that would likely weaken the quality and accessibility of available data, such as publishing only “relevant” data at an “aggregated level”, and only with permission of the landowner and manager. If these amendments are brought into the final legislation, the nature of the available data will likely not serve carbon certification projects.

Nature Restoration Law

The Nature Restoration Law was adopted in June last year and entered into force in August. Under its Article 1, the law sets EU targets for the restoration of EU land and sea (2030: restoration measures on 20% of the area with the possibility to focus on Natura 2000 sites, and 2050: measures in place for all ecosystems in need of restoration). The law has both area-based and indicator-based targets at the MS level, which MS need to reach through the implementation of their Nature Restoration Plans which are due in final version in 2027. Agro-ecosystems are one of the nine ecosystems which fall under restoration targets and obligations. Targets for this ecosystem aim to enhance the biodiversity of agricultural ecosystems (in addition to protected habitats) and do so with indicators such as the grassland butterfly index, the SOC in cropland mineral soils, share of UAA with high-diversity landscape features, of which MS must select two, together with the mandatory common farmland bird index. Besides the agro-ecosystems indicators, there is a dedicated article on pollinator populations that is relevant for agriculture, aiming to improve pollinator diversity and reverse decline by 2030, followed by a positive trend until satisfactory levels are reached. Each indicator will have to be monitored against a satisfactory level which is set by the MS following Commission guidance, and also the monitoring frequency will differ per indicator. SOC and high diversity landscape features, for example, will have to be monitored at least every six years, while the grassland butterfly and farmland bird indices require yearly monitoring.

Although the NRL indicators are not automatically transferable between Member State-level and project-level schemes, as in the case of the SML, their transferability seems more feasible here than with the SML's soil biodiversity metric. However, while the SML's soil biodiversity metric would likely be too demanding for a credit scheme in terms of MRV, the Member State-level indicators in the NRL risk being too lenient. It has been suggested in the CRCF draft methodology that the mandatory biodiversity criteria can be met by monitoring and proving a benefit to one of the NRL indicators. However, this would include SOC, which, as mentioned in the discussion of the SML, by itself is not sufficient to demonstrate a contribution to biodiversity and should also not be accepted as a co-benefit in first place since it is already the primary focus of the units that will be certified under the CRCF. Still, in the CRCF it has been challenging to go beyond NRL biodiversity indicators, due to the level of information required to set appropriate indicators and determine thresholds that may be applicable across the EU, and out of consideration for the cost levels that may cause operators to be reluctant to take up the

schemes if there are too many burdensome requirements. The [Commission's guidance](#) for MS on the methodology for the monitoring of high diversity landscape features published early 2025 may be an additional source of inspiration for the CRCF methodologies.

The NRL is a driver for more sustainable management and the restoration of ecosystems, including agricultural ones. However, several elements point to the fact that, despite MS being required to monitor a certain set of indicators for agro-ecosystems, agricultural mineral soils might not be the main area of focus. Up to 2030, MS can prioritise Natura 2000 sites, which may cause the impetus of the NRL to be off to a slower start when it comes to the restoration of agricultural land. Furthermore, an emergency break article has been added to the NRL, which allows the Commission to adopt an Implementing Act with an initial duration of one year which suspends the restoration of agro-ecosystems in the case of force majeure events which cause a need for additional agriculture production to ensure security for EU food consumption. On carbon sequestration specifically, the NRL emphasises the importance of nature-based carbon sequestration, and the need to restore, enhance, and protect ecosystems with high potential for carbon removal and storage, which might again prioritise other ecosystems over agricultural land.

CRCF business case

The opportunity for the CRCF to help build data availability and achieve ecosystem restoration and climate targets depends on the final form the methodologies will take, and the interoperability with different policies and instruments discussed in the previous sections. Another factor which will determine its impact to a large extent, will be the degree of uptake that the scheme will engender. Therefore, it is important to reflect on its “business case”.

The place for CRCF units in a compliance setting is uncertain at this stage. Existing EU environmental and agricultural policy prescribes certain practices and bans others, and sets thresholds and targets, in which credits, so far, do not have an immediate use case. At the same time, many of the wider agri-food supply chain regulations laying out the rules for trade, investment, target setting, and reporting, such as the Corporate Sustainability Reporting Directive (CSRD) Corporate Sustainability Due Diligence Directive (CSDDD), Green Claims Directive (GCD), EU Taxonomy (still missing agriculture), have not yet been finalised, or have been announced to be reopened for amendments. Also the discussion around a potential market-based instrument to reduce emissions and enhance carbon sequestration in the agricultural sector is still at an exploratory stage, raising questions around the potential demand and use case for CRCF carbon farming credits. The Unfair Commercial Practices Directive already banned the use of credits for offsetting for product claims, and the GCD, currently under negotiation, will further regulate what type of claims will be allowed at company level: compensation or contribution claims, compensation of residual or remaining emissions, fossil or non-fossil emissions, and using permanent removals or temporary sequestration.

The type of regulations around the primary sector, and the current uncertainty in the development of the value chain regulations, make credits mostly something that can be found in the voluntary realm, so far. In that voluntary investment sphere, a wide array of voluntary schemes and standards exist for the certification and reporting of sustainability initiatives, such as Science Based Targets initiative (SBTi) for the target setting, certification methodologies such as Verra and Gold Standard to, in principle, ensure quality, Voluntary Carbon Markets Initiative (VCMI) for the responsible use of credits, Carbon Disclosure Project (CDP) for reporting, ESG ratings to translate efforts into shareholder value, and benchmarks to increase transparency. Over the past years, the voluntary carbon market and many of the abovementioned initiatives have come under

increasing scrutiny due to concerns around their quality, reliability, and governance. The issues that have been uncovered have eroded trust and affected the appetite for this approach. On top of that, mitigation deterrence, where companies offset their emissions by purchasing credits, rather than pursue emission reductions, remains at the forefront of concerns in the voluntary carbon market system. At the same time, a different model has been developing in the agricultural sector, under the concept of regenerative agriculture, with organisations such as the Sustainable Agriculture Initiative (SAI platform), the World Business Council for Sustainable Development, the One Planet Business for Biodiversity, and Verra providing frameworks with tools and metrics to make agriculture more sustainable, including by reducing emissions and increasing removals alongside many other objectives, in ways that do not entail the use of credits in an offsetting or compensation logic.

New policy options for climate change mitigation in the agri-food value chain

The 2023 study by Trinomics investigated the suitability of an agri-food Emissions Trading System (ETS) for reducing greenhouse gas emissions and increasing carbon removals in the agricultural sector. The study also explored five different design options for such ETS, and explored the potential integration of CRCF units, as the methodology to generate the credits for the emission reductions and emission removals in such systems. The study covered two methods for the MRV of on-farm emissions: a default method using emission factors, and a voluntary opt-in method using CRCF-certified on-farm data. In a scenario where not all farms would be covered under the system, non-obligated parties could still voluntarily participate by generating (CRCF) credits and selling them to obligated parties to meet their obligations under the ETS. This could, with significant implications for the ETS cap on emissions, be applied to an ETS, regardless of its “point of obligation”, whether the regulated entity is upstream such as in the case of feed and fertiliser producers, on-farm, or downstream such as in the case of food processors or retailers.

In 2024, a follow-up study was launched which aims to develop a better understanding of different potential market-based policy options. The policy options currently in the scope of the study include Carbon Farming Public Procurement, Mandatory Climate Standards which could apply to feed producers, food processors, retailers, or other downstream actors, and an Agri-food ETS which could cover upstream and/or downstream actors such as feed producers and food processors, or farms.

The Carbon Farming Public Procurement option is looking to boost financing for the CRCF units by fostering an EU market for CRCF units. The procurement system managed by the EU Commission could use different types of mechanisms like feed-in-tariffs and reverse auctioning or forward contracts by public authorities such as the Commission or MS. This would secure a steady demand and, depending on the mechanism, price for the units, which could incentivise farmers to participate in the generation of these units. From this centralised pool which would distinguish between emission reduction and emission removal credits, private actors can purchase the units on a voluntary basis, allowing private investment to complement public investment. An important aspect to consider is that State Aid rules under competition law need to be taken into consideration in the design of the credit system. In case some competitive bidding mechanism is used, this is likely to not create issues, whereas in the case of fixed prices or price guarantees, there may be conflicts.

The Mandatory Climate Standards option would set an emission reduction target, including scope 3 emissions, alongside an emission removal target for one or multiple levels of entities in the agri-food value chain. These obligations would link to current corporate climate commitments and reporting requirements, and the CRCF could serve as the tool for implementation. By using CRCF units, companies can reduce their emissions and increase their removals by changing suppliers and buying CRCF units directly within their supply chain, whereas with default emission factors they would be limited to changing their product portfolio in terms of the throughput/volume of high emissive products and ingredients (e.g. decreasing meat/substituting with alternatives) and/or buying credits from a centralised pool.

Finally, also in the Agri ETS options, three approaches could be taken for compliance under the default method: 1) obligated entities can comply by purchasing allowances through an auction platform; 2) obligated entities could purchase CRCF units from a centralised pool; or 3) obligated entities could change their product portfolios in terms of the throughput/volume of high emissive products and ingredients. A public authority such as a Carbon Central Bank would control the amount of emission reduction and emission removal allowances in the system as well as the centralised pool for the buying and selling of CRCF units. Under the certified method, compliance can be achieved by changing product portfolios, changing suppliers, or purchasing CRCF units directly from their suppliers.

Across policy design options which would entail the purchase of CRCF carbon farming credits by certain actors, the question of which type of actors should be allowed to do so is relevant and may determine the magnitude of the demand for CRCF credits as well as their price. In a direct supply chain approach, only obligated entities could buy credits, and only those generated by farmers or land managers in their direct supply chain. This could be done either through contracts combining food and carbon delivery, or separate contracts. In an agri-food value chain market approach, any actor in the agri-food sector could purchase the credits from all farmers or land managers in the supply chain of similar entities, through a separate contract for carbon delivery. Finally, in an open market approach, any entity from any sector, private or public, would be able to purchase credits from any farmer or land manager through a centralised credit pool.

While the CRCF, given the right considerations in its methodologies, could be an enabler for sustainable practices, demand for CRCF credits needs to be subject to strong governance that can ensure the necessary precautions around the use of nature based temporary carbon sequestration units. The question of whether such credits would be appropriate for compensation claims is disputed among stakeholders with many pointing out the inequivalence between temporary sequestration and emissions with long atmospheric lifetimes. Some state that as long as contribution claims are not commercially attractive, public funds should be used, through public procurement, or the CAP. This makes it, in the current market conditions, difficult to bring in private finance which leads other stakeholders to advocate for allowing compensation claims as long as the quality of the credits is considered high, and their use responsible. The policy options discussed here which may have huge effects on the uptake of CRCF are still very much under hypothetical discussion, and nothing may come of it. Some of these policy options, would in their turn again need to be integrated into the wider policy environment. For example, the MCS would need to be aligned with reporting regulation under the CSRD.

Public-private funding

Various sources of funding, public and private, are relevant for financing carbon farming. A blended finance approach in which public funding, for example through the CAP, covers overhead or transition costs or transaction costs of certification could be done, if a clear line can be drawn between the different stages of public and consequent private funding, to avoid the issue of double funding for a single action, which under private standards is not allowed. On the one hand, this may engage certain farmers that would otherwise not be incentivised or able to change their practices. On the other hand, it does

mean that public money is facilitating access to crediting schemes, potentially on the voluntary carbon market, which may not be an appropriate use of public funding. Moreover, depending on the certification schemes, access may not be suitable for or benefit all farmers. In any case, should a credit be generated through an activity that earlier received public funding, a part of the outcome proportional to the share of funding should be attributed to the public funding instead of the private investor. From the perspective of competition law, however, the blended finance approach potentially constitutes an issue of double funding or of proportionality of State aid. Hence, there are ongoing discussions around the introduction of a clawback mechanism for situations in which public money goes into the farming sector through the CAP or State Aid, which later leads to revenues from credit trading schemes (be it public or private).

There is a general agreement that public money should be used for public goods, going there where needed most and yielding the largest benefits to society. The activity- versus result-based scheme debate revolves, to a large extent, around how this requirement can best be met in agriculture. Through the CAP, public money is available for the provision of farm advisory services. However, 72% of farmers in the EU only rely on practical experience. Given the skills and knowledge needed for sustainable carbon farming, this is a use of public funding that should be strengthened.

The monetary incentive on result-based carbon farming may have unwanted socio-economic effects that should also be considered. Access to land and land prices are a large factor in determining which type of farms see today and will see in the future in the EU. About half of the EU UAA is being rented, meaning that those who work it, do not own it. This could have an impact on the attractiveness of carbon farming practices, since building up soil health is a long-term investment in the land, which may not pay off for an individual operator if there are doubts on their activity on that land in the long term. Furthermore, as the land improves, its value rises, which in the first place benefits the owner of the land rather than the farmer if their contributions would not be fairly rewarded.

Another potential role that public funding could play, possibly without running into the issue of double funding, is developing cost effective MRV for carbon and co-benefits, which is still lacking. This investment would lead to better and more cost effective MRV, which would benefit the robustness of the certification and improve access for operators. However, the question comes down to whether investment needed for creating infrastructure and knowledge for a result-based system would be used better, with a larger environmental and climate impact, on directly supporting changes on the ground

through simpler and more accessible schemes such as activity-based incentives for proven practices.

Conclusion

The CRCF is an attempt at creating an enabling framework for carbon farming that can deliver on environmental objectives as well as create an attractive business model to pull private sector funds into the land sectors in the hope to enable a transition. Permanence, environmental integrity, liability, additionality, and economic viability are all considerations in the framework, but as this Focus Group has discussed, it is unlikely for the CRCF to satisfy all these aspects without using the synergies with other policy instruments. As a result, while everyone agrees that action is needed, many questions remain to be addressed in the efforts to establish a policy environment that is not only conducive to carbon farming, but also addresses challenges across environment, climate, and society in a holistic manner.

The CRCF has been designed around climate change mitigation, but if there is a drive to move towards more result-based systems overall, similar approaches would have to be developed for other societal objectives (e.g. biodiversity enhancement, water use and quality, etc.). CAP data gathering and reporting is evolving and becoming more granular. While there is room for improvement in the current overall use and distribution of CAP funding, a lot of issues and unanswered questions stand in the way of making the CAP more result-based. Using the CRCF methodology for the granting of CAP funds does not seem an immediate avenue for a series of reasons: it relies heavily on additionality, which is challenging to apply to all situations (for example rewarding maintenance of carbon stocks and pioneers), requires insurances to cover liability and impacts caused by external factors, and it is not clear whether a result-based system for agriculture would be compatible with competition rules. Moreover, the question remains whether a result-based system would be appropriate for all actions funded by CAP, given the relatively high MRV costs associated with such system. It is clear that for the time being, activity-based incentives are crucial to support activities that have the potential to deliver results but that do not fit completely in a result-based scheme for any number of reasons.

With the SML still under negotiation and the CRCF methodology still under development, a lot of question marks remain. Is the data from both systems going to be “interoperable”? Will we have similar indicators, similar methodologies, will the information be comparable? At this stage, it seems that there are similarities on some points, such as the selected ISO standards for determining SOC and bulk density, and some of the indicators or descriptors that are being considered. On the other hand, there are clear

differences between the two laws, with the SML covering a limited number of sampling points, and possibly restricting availability and accessibility of collected data. The discussion under the SML on the appropriate descriptor for soil biodiversity could inform sustainability requirements, in particular the biodiversity requirement, under the CRCF. The data gathered under the SML could, together with IACS and LUCAS data, inform the standardised baselines that are likely to be a part of the CRCF methodology and support the development of models that could be used for quantification. However, given the timing discrepancy of the CRCF aiming to be operational in 2026, while the first data on a relatively limited number of samples under the SML will come in around 2029, it seems like in first instance, SML data is unlikely to support the CRCF during its initial implementation period.

By being attractive to farmers, the CRCF could drive plot-level activities with restoring effects on agricultural land, where the NRL might not provide that stimulus at first. Also when it comes to SOC quantification and monitoring, the CRCF might support the NRL, rather than the other way around. The CRCF is intended to incentivise practices that lead to results that can support the achievement of the NRL targets. In doing so, it will generate the needed data at a granular level and with monitoring that is more frequent than what is required at MS level under the NRL. Also for indicators other than SOC, the CRCF may provide useful information on the NRL targets, but since the Nature Restoration Plans and some of the indicators are still being drafted, it is early to say whether the CRCF data will be relevant for the NRL and could be used at MS level. An important consideration, however, is that depending on uptake, the CRCF may be capturing a specific segment of farmers, meaning that data would not necessarily be representative of all farmers on all agricultural land at MS level. Important to consider also are issues with additionality. SML and NRL obligations on MS need to be taken into account when determining whether an activity is additional or not and whether it is possible for operators or groups of operators to obtain CRCF certificates.

There is considerable scope to restore Europe's degraded soils and build up SOC, thus contributing to climate change mitigation. This potential should be exploited. It is then a subsequent question of how this will be achieved: through support for holistic changes to farming systems (agroecology, organic, regenerative, etc.), support for specific actions (cover crops, agroforestry as currently supported under the CAP), or through generation of carbon credits. As it stands now, the regulatory and voluntary investment spaces provide mixed signals towards the question of uptake of CRCF credits. Depending on

how policies such as the Green Claims Directive develop, they may end up increasing voluntary demand for credits, to which the CRCF carbon farming units could cater, or they may reduce demand by introducing certain limitations. This has implications for potential greenwashing and mitigation deterrence - especially considering the temporary nature of CRCF carbon farming units. In a voluntary context, elements in the final design of the CRCF methodologies, such as the baseline and the monitoring requirements, may also influence the scheme's uptake. The temporary nature of the CRCF carbon farming credits which accurately reflect the impermanence and vulnerability of the carbon stored in biogenic carbon pools likely adds to the challenge of bringing these credits into the market. On the other hand, a new system such as an Agri ETS or MCS could be set up with the CRCF units as its building blocks, creating a compliance market for the credits. The degree to which these compliance systems will drive the demand for emission reduction, carbon removal credits, or both, will depend on the targets that are set for each, and whether a certain degree of flexibility between the two would be allowed.

4. Summary of recommendations

1. The terms “activity”, “practice”, and “action” are used across different policies, sometimes interchangeably, sometimes denoting different meanings. The same is true for the terms “output”, “result”, and “impact”. Policy discussions would benefit from greater clarity if terms were properly defined and used consistently.
2. Data that is already being gathered, in the CAP, and through other avenues, could be leveraged better to support the operators participating in the CRCF and bring down MRV costs. Therefore, even though policies target different scales and scopes, and occur on different timelines, there needs to be increased attention for the complementarity and interoperability of data from different sources. The recent interest in a “benchmarking” exercise in EU agriculture, though at this stage not yet defined, and likely voluntary, might facilitate the harmonisation of indicators and requirements.
3. There are advantages and disadvantages to the activity-based support of the CAP, and the result-based incentives of the CRCF. Both have a place, and full integration making the CAP a purely result-based system using CRCF methodologies might be feasible in the future, but in the short term would encounter issues, such as regulatory limitations, but also cost of MRV. On the other hand, a combination of these funding opportunities could create an enabling mix to deliver more effective climate action.
4. The indicators under discussion in the SML need to be considered to ensure maximum synergy opportunities, such as the CRCF supporting the SML with additional data points, and SML data supporting the baselines and the science under the CRCF. While the full implementation of the SML will take time, it is important to carefully consider the indicator question in the first CRCF methodology, since adjusting it later may be slow, and the updated version may not be implemented retroactively.
5. Although a balance needs to be struck between the robustness of the certification methodologies and the practical accessibility of the scheme, the CRCF is proposed as a climate instrument and the use case of the units is unclear (compensation of emissions in voluntary and compliance approaches is possible). Therefore, environmental integrity is an absolute priority that cannot be traded off.

6. Scientifically robust and cost-effective soil biodiversity indicators need to be developed through living labs that can make measuring below-ground biodiversity an integral part of the CRCF. If farmers get credits for storing more carbon in soil, the biodiversity co-benefit should also be proven in the soil since the correlation between above- and below-ground biodiversity is not always straightforward.
7. The CRCF needs to go beyond SOC as an indicator for biodiversity. The Soil Monitoring Law proposal includes a specific, albeit incomplete, list of descriptors to measure soil biodiversity – an aspect that the co-legislators have not disputed but rather improved. Hence, discussions on the SML show that descriptors beyond SOC are needed to assess the impact of specific practices on taxonomic and functional soil biodiversity, and that it should not be considered the only indicator under the CRCF.
8. In order to allow for interoperability of data, information gathered under the SML should be accessible in raw and non-aggregated form in order to better support the further development and amendment of the baseline in the CRCF.
9. The SML should define a clear objective and implement concrete measures towards achieving healthy soils across the EU by 2050. Achieving and maintaining a good condition of the soil ecosystem is a precondition for long-term carbon storage also for individual projects.
10. A compliance mechanism needs to be created to supplement voluntary action and drive investment in agricultural practices that deliver enhanced high-quality emission reduction and carbon sequestration with sustainability co-benefits. While voluntary action is already taking place, relying on it alone will not enable public and private actors to achieve the EU climate targets and a transition of the agricultural sector towards sustainability.
11. A compliance mechanism could start with default emission factors to make the scheme accessible and gradually integrate on-farm MRV to increase accuracy and robustness. Such a “default emissions factor scheme” would not require or utilise the CRCF, which has a more complicated (and accurate) quantification approach. The decision to start with a simple default approach would reflect balancing the needs for a robust system that is also implementable. Such a balance should not come at a cost to environmental integrity, hence emission factors should be made sure not to underestimate emissions.

12. Agricultural emission reductions need to be separated from carbon sequestration in land and biomass. The same mechanisms could be used for achieving both, but separate targets are needed to ensure there is no fungibility, and no flexibility should be allowed. They are not equivalent in climate terms and hence should not be treated as such.
13. Public money use needs to be targeted towards the largest impact on the public good. Strengthening the public provision of farm advisory services and supporting the implementation of proven methods are high-impact, high-integrity, no-regret measures. A carbon credit has no intrinsic value and has in the past not been a guarantee for positive change. Hence, the objective is not to create an enabling environment for CRCF credits per se. What matters is the change on the ground which leads to improved environmental and climate benefits.

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